

ON THE ROAD TO SUSTAINABILITY: PAVING THE WAY FOR
OPERAS AS AN EFFICIENT OPEN SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES
SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

OPERAS

Pathfinder Service

DELIVERABLE 5.3

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ON THE ROAD TO SUSTAINABILITY: PAVING THE WAY FOR OPERAS AS AN
EFFICIENT OPEN SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES SCHOLARLY
COMMUNICATION RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

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TERMINOLOGY

API	Application Programming Interface
OA	Open Access
OLA	Operational Level Agreement
PSP	Publishing Service Providers (Pathfinder's early "code name")
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
SPM	Service Portfolio Management
SMS	Service Management System
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TS	TypeScript
UI	User Interface
UX	User Experience

Abstract

This deliverable presents the implementation of the Pathfinder platform as part of task T5.3 of the OPERAS-PLUS project. The main goal of the Pathfinder is to help editors and editorial managers in discovering publishing services for their editorial responsibilities within the realm of open access publications in social sciences and humanities, including journals, books, editions, and other research outputs.

Serving as a comprehensive catalogue, the Pathfinder presents scholarly communication services provided by OPERAS members and potentially other providers. Its purpose is to support researchers acting as editors and editorial managers, to ease and enhance the quality of their work. Authors can also use the Pathfinder to receive recommendations for publishing their research findings.

The document, which starts from a general presentation of the origin of this service, analyses in-depth the characteristics of the Pathfinder in the context of the whole OPERAS ecosystem. Details on how its implementation has been carried out in OPERAS-PLUS are also presented.

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Executive summary

Pathfinder aims at helping editors and editorial managers to find publishing services that they can use to perform their editorial tasks on open access publications in social sciences and humanities, such as journals, books, editions and other research outputs.

Pathfinder works as a catalogue where scholarly communication services are offered, mainly by OPERAS members but possibly from other providers as well, to researchers acting as editors and editorial managers to support their work and improve its quality. Authors can also use the Pathfinder to receive suggestions for publishing the results of their research.

The original prototype of the Pathfinder was developed as part of the OPERAS-P research project, funded under the Horizon 2020 work programme, which ran from June 2019 to June 2021. In the context of the OPERAS-PLUS project, the platform has been completely refactored and developed anew by using modern web technologies. In particular, a back-office web application has been implemented to ease the data collection and update of the catalogue. Also, personalised services for registered users are now available.

The present deliverable describes the characteristics of the service in the context of the OPERAS ecosystem, presenting also the development process, its implementation.

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1. Introduction

This document provides an overview of the work conducted in Task 5.3 of the OPERAS-PLUS project, focusing on the implementation of the Pathfinder platform.

The overall structure of the document follows the standardised template that OPERAS uses as part of its Service Portfolio Management (SPM) process, which was originally based on the FitSM standard template called “Service Design and Transition Package”¹. Each of the individual OPERAS services will follow a similar structure, which will enable all content generated to be directly used within the OPERAS service management system (SMS).

Therefore, this document is structured as follows:

- Section 1 introduces the doc (this section)
- Section 2 discusses the origins of the platform as a prototype of a previous research project (OPERAS-P).
- Section 3 assesses the platform's overall value proposition.
- Section 4 explores potential business cases, considering market dynamics, costs, risks, and other relevant factors for when the service becomes publicly available.
- Section 5 presents an in-depth analysis of the operational aspects of the Pathfinder, considering both technical and financial considerations. It also presents the data entry strategies for the platform envisioned in the OPERAS-PLUS project.
- Section 6 outlines the necessary steps and considerations for transitioning the service from the development phase to the operational phase.
- Lastly, section 7 provides a detailed account of the software development process behind the Pathfinder, covering various stages such as UX/UI design, data modelling, implementation of business logic and APIs, and front-end development for end-users.

¹ <https://www.fitsm.eu/downloads/#toggle-id-5>

2. Background

The origin of the Pathfinder lies in the OPERAS-P project², which ended in June 2021. The result was a working prototype developed by Lexis and hosted at the premises of the University of Turin.

The platform, originally described in an OPERAS-P deliverable D4.1: Common Access Point to Publication Services Specifications³, was developed by assessing the possible needs of the target users through two questionnaires, the first for OPERAS members, who were called to identify and list the relevant services they provide, and the second, for SSH researchers, in order to guide the design of the user interface.

At the same time, this process also allowed the collection of all the data inside the prototype's database. The Pathfinder acted as a search engine to let users look for and browse these data. Therefore, there were two main functionalities:

- Common Scenarios: where users could find a selection of the most frequent requests.

Image 1: Old Pathfinder's Common Scenarios

² <https://operas-eu.org/projects/past-projects/operas-p/>

³ <https://zenodo.org/record/4817727>

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- Detailed Research: a sophisticated search interface through which the users could query the entire database of available publishing services and items, selecting one or more entries within different macro-areas. Users could also query by entering a single or several words (separated by space, comma or the '+' sign) in the text space at the top right.

The image shows a screenshot of the Pathfinder website's 'Detailed Research' form. The header includes the Pathfinder logo and the tagline 'Find your way in the maze of academic publishing in social sciences and humanities'. Navigation links for 'HOW IT WORKS', 'COMMON SCENARIOS', 'DETAILED RESEARCH', and 'LOGIN' are visible. A search bar is located at the top right. The main section is titled 'Detailed Research' and contains several expandable sections, each with a plus icon and a help icon:

- BASIC INFORMATION ABOUT YOUR PROJECT**
- TYPE OF PUBLICATION AND FORMATS**
- YOUR PEER REVIEW REQUIREMENTS**
 - What kind of peer review do you need?
 - review proposal
 - review sample
 - review full manuscript
 - review preprint
 - review abstract
 - before submission
 - after submission
 - after publication
 - single reviewer
 - multiple reviewers
 - editorial board only
 - crowdsourced review
 - single blind
 - double blind
 - not blind
 - open review
 - Do you need to use a specific tool for managing peer review?
 - Dspace
 - Episciences
 - Open Journal System (OJS)
 - Open Monograph Press (OMP)
 - Publons
 - not finding what you look for?
- SUBMITTING YOUR CONTENT**
- ARCHIVING AND LONG-TERM PRESERVATION**
- ACCESS TO YOUR WORK AFTER PUBLICATION**
- YOUR COPYRIGHT REQUIREMENTS**
- STANDARD IDENTIFIERS**
 - Do you need to use any of these standard identifiers?
 - Digital Object Identifier (DOI)
 - Open Researcher and Contributor ID (ORCID)
 - International Standard Book Number (ISBN)
 - International Standard Serial Number (ISSN)
 - Uniform Resource Name (URN)
 - Other Handle System protocols
 - CIÊNCIA ID
 - not finding what you look for?
- DISSEMINATION AND MARKETING REQUIREMENTS**
- READERSHIP STATISTICS AND MEASURES OF IMPACT**
- ADDITIONAL REQUIREMENTS**

At the bottom of the form is a red 'SUBMIT' button. The footer contains the text 'OPERAS Pathfinder 2020. Terms of use', 'Privacy policy', and 'Credits'.

Image 2: Old Pathfinder's Detailed Research

In both cases, the Pathfinder showed a list of OPERAS members sorted according to

the corresponding query. Clicking on their name a detailed list of all the solutions they provide, plus information on them including a link to their website and a contact email address, were presented.

The screenshot shows the Pathfinder website interface. At the top, it says 'Find your way in the maze of academic publishing in social sciences and humanities'. Below the search bar, it indicates '12 record found'. The search filters are set to 'Digital Object Identifier (DOI)'. The main result is 'Lexis' from the 'Italian National Research Council (CNR)'. A detailed description of Lexis follows, covering various aspects like publication types, subject areas, languages, scientific validation, peer review, licenses, access policy, and more. Below this, a list of other service providers is shown, each with a name and a contact icon.

Image 3: Old Pathfinder's Service and Service Providers description

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Based on the design study and the prototype developed during the OPERAS-P project, the objective within OPERAS-PLUS was to support the technical development of the service into production (TRL9), offering a common access point towards the scholarly communication services offered by the OPERAS community.

This included code development and an update of the database structure.

Early on in OPERAS-PLUS, it was decided that a design refresh was required, thus triggering a number of user design workshops with potential users.

Therefore, though this slightly delayed the development phase, it ultimately proved valuable to ensure that the final product was both “modern”, in terms of adhering to current web standards as well as look and feel, while also better matching user requirements.

3. Value Proposition

User Profile	Description
(Potential) Customer of the service	Publishing Service Providers (SSH focused). Main provisioners of information. Moving forward, though at present, the service is free for everyone, a possible exploitation strategy might be considered where Service Providers have premium functionalities i.e. the possibility to update in autonomy the description of their publishing services.
(Potential) User of the service	Editors, Editorial Managers. In particular, Editorial managers can be journals editors-in-chief, book series lead editors and/or directors of scholar-led (but not exclusively) publishers, librarians involved in providing advice and services to scholars or in managing library publishing services. Also Authors albeit they are not the main target of the platform.
User profile (pains/gains)	Editors: to find the services needed to curate and prepare a publication Editorial managers, overseeing the production and publication of research outputs: to find the suitable services to operate and manage an editorial initiative Authors: to look for a publisher for their books or for a journal (in case they want to publish an article)
Service Description	Pathfinder assists editors and editorial managers in the social sciences and humanities to discover publishing services for their editorial tasks on open access publications, including journals, books, editions, and other research outputs. Pathfinder operates as a catalogue that presents scholarly communication services, mainly provided by OPERAS members, with the possibility of additional offerings from other providers. This service aims to support editors and editorial managers in improving the quality of their work and enhancing the overall scholarly communication landscape.

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	Authors can also use the Pathfinder to receive suggestions for publishing the results of their research.
Service Area	Discovery
Service tags	editorial services, service providers, editors, editorial managers, open access, publications, social sciences and humanities, scholarly communication, publishing services
Value Proposition (pain relievers / gain creators)	<p>Pains: Services that are needed to create, run and promote SSH publications are very diverse and not so easily findable.</p> <p>Gains: A single place to find these kinds of services, independently of the nature of the publication being worked on.</p> <p>Value: Streamlined workflow for editors and editorial managers, also offering tailored suggestions to authors seeking publishing opportunities.</p>
Tagline	Find your way in the maze of academic publishing in social sciences and humanities.
Service Criticality	Mission critical for OPERAS
EOSC Marketplace	Not yet

Table 1: Value Proposition Design

4. Business Case Design

	Best Case	Average Case	Worst Case
Demand assessment	<p>A good number of visitors (1000s). A fair number of registered users (100s). A significant number of services (>250) and service providers (>25) described in the platform.</p>	<p>An average number of visitors (<1000). An average to low number of registered users (<100). An average number of services (100-250) and service providers (10-25) described in the platform.</p>	<p>An average to low number of visitors (<500). A low number of registered users (<50). A limited number of services (< 100) and service providers (<10) described in the platform.</p>
Assumptions (about uptake)	<p>High uptake due to positive user feedback and word-of-mouth recommendations, resulting in a significant increase in user engagement. A successful response from service providers leads to an increase of data in the platform.</p>	<p>Moderate uptake, which leads to a slow growth of the number of users of the platform. Only OPERAS members provide descriptions to populate the catalogue.</p>	<p>Low uptake due to limited user engagement and negative feedback, resulting in a decrease in users. Limited answers from OPERAS members as well, which leads to a not-so-rich catalogue.</p>
Expected organisational impact	<p>Possibly the need to increase the hosting capabilities.</p>	<p>Data entry works as expected, possibly a bit lower.</p>	<p>Lower data entry works but compensated by the higher effort in</p>

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	<p>More data entry work.</p> <p>Substantially raises OPERAS position in open scholarly publishing, potentially internationally</p>	<p>Reinforces OPERAS mission in supporting open scholarly publishing</p>	<p>trying and reaching out to service providers</p>
Expected Cost	<p>8 PM/year due to expected higher number of feature requests</p> <p>2.000 €/year hosting for increased data and processing</p> <p>4 PM/year for data entry and maintenance</p>	<p>4 PM/year for doing small software evolution and for supporting platform's operation</p> <p>1.000 €/year hosting</p> <p>2 PM/year for data entry and maintenance</p>	<p>2 PM/year minimum maintenance</p> <p>800 €/year hosting requirements low</p> <p>8 PM/year in order to improve the quality of the catalogue</p>
Expected Revenue / Cost Recovery	<p>Full costs covered by OPERAS members (member states in ERIC)</p> <p>A small annual fee for Service Providers to manage their catalogue content.</p> <p>Other OPERAS funded projects for further development.</p>	<p>Operation costs partially covered by OPERAS. New projects or national funding continue evolving service.</p> <p>Data entry/maintenance activities supported by OPERAS national nodes done voluntarily.</p> <p>Synergies with other OPERAS funded projects (e.g. DIAMAS) to be stressed.</p>	<p>No costs are covered, and all are supported by in-kind efforts. No future projects where service could be supported.</p>

Risks	None in terms of financial effects and technical aspects. The current platform hosting option, and the budget allocated for it, allow to accommodate a higher user access.	None in terms of financial effects. Possibly a higher impact on dissemination, as more effort will be needed in order to improve the visibility of the platform.	None in terms of financial effects. A higher impact on dissemination, as more effort will be needed in order to improve the visibility of the platform.
Supplier Evaluation	The platform has been developed and maintained by OPERAS-PLUS partners Net7 and Lexis. The only external supplier is the cloud provider, Hetzner ⁴ , one of the European leaders in this field. Moving forward, the platform will continue to need developers and a cloud provider (potentially a public infrastructure provider), data entry and content managers, as well as marketing and dissemination should OPERAS have internal resource constraints.		
Constraints / limiting factors	Pathfinder is a data driven initiative: the higher the number of entries in its catalogue, the larger might be its potential audience.		
Competitors and/or similar services	Potentially the SSHOC marketplace ⁵ for a limited number of categories (e.g. training). The other similar services are in reality catalogues of single providers, presenting their offering.		
Pricing and/or Access Policy	For the moment: free to use for final users; no fee requested to service providers to appear in the catalogue. As a possible future exploitation strategy, it could be considered a recurrent fee for service providers who want to autonomously manage the description of their services.		

Table 2: Business Case Design

⁴ <https://hetzner.com/>

⁵ <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/>

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Service Design

4.1. Service Requirements

<p>Functional and technical</p>	<p>The Pathfinder is a web platform that can be deployed in a physical or virtual server. Its suggested, but not required, deployment is on a Linux based server, with the Docker containerisation technology, accessible online at the 22 (SSH, for installation and maintenance) and 443 (TLS, for secure web access) ports.</p> <p>Its development and deployment have been carried out by using a complete stack of open source frameworks and products, namely:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Laravel and Backpack for the back-end and back-office PHP-based development ● Angular, for the TypeScript/JavaScript front-end development ● MariaDB as relational database management system (RDBMS) ● the Elasticsearch search server ● NGINX as the web server ● FastCGI Process Manager (PHP-FPM) as a PHP interpreter ● Docker as the virtualisation technology.
<p>Availability, continuity and performance-related</p>	<p>The Pathfinder should be available 24/7 with a 95-98% availability target.</p>
<p>Security and data protection-related</p>	<p>No specific sensitive data is and will be managed in the Pathfinder. Regular data privacy policies to apply (GDPR), i.e. user registrations.</p>
<p>Usability-related</p>	<p>As Pathfinder is an end-user service, the UI needs to be designed for ease of use, effectiveness, efficiency and user satisfaction, and to support mobile browsing to deliver a seamless experience for users across various devices.</p>

Organisational	Coordination required between OPERAS for strategic alignment, Net7 for software development and the hosting of the platform, and Lexis for performing data entry.
Data sources	Manual collection by Lexis and data curation for the catalogue via interacting directly with selected data providers. This workflow will continue for the rest of the project. Possibly, from the DIAMAS project, online application for collecting new providers and offers, and/or backend access for self-provision.

Table 3: Service Requirements

4.2. Service Architecture

4.2.1. Data entry and database management

The process of gathering data for integration into the database is managed by Lexis, as detailed below. Initially, we undertook the formalisation of the publishing workflow in SSH. Drawing insights from analogous works and leveraging the expertise of fellow OPERAS-PLUS consortium members, who possessed pertinent skills in publishing and were proficient native English speakers (as English was deliberately selected as the standard language), we collaboratively developed the table labelled O2_SERVICES-LIST.xlsx, which is presented subsequently. This table outlines potential categories of services for inclusion in the Pathfinder. Furthermore, it serves as a foundational framework for shared taxonomies and a glossary, catering to future contributors in these domains.

Net7 utilised this table to construct the database architecture of the platform. Its contents are subject to updates, enhancements, and augmentations in line with the practical utilisation of the Pathfinder, coupled with feedback garnered from both users and service providers.

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02_SERVICES-LIST.xlsx

PHASE	FAMILY	SERVICE NAME	DISAMBIGUATION
PRE-PUBLISHING	Editorial	call for papers	launch and management of call for papers process
		peer review	peer review process management
	Administrative, legal and financial	submission management	administrative work supporting receipt and management of submissions/proposals
		anti-plagiarism	text anti-plagiarism check
	Funding	project management	administrative procedures required to start the publishing project (journal or monograph series, or publishing house/brand)
contracts		drafting, checking, archiving, management of publishing contracts	
PUBLISHING	Production	licensing	licence attribution to the editorial content
		accounting	accounting management (invoicing)
		third-party permissions and images right	clearance and licensing of any images/content owned by third party rights holders
POST-PUBLISHING	Communication and marketing	publication fees	management of publication fees
		crowdfunding	initiation and management of crowdfunding campaigns to source funding
POST-PUBLISHING	Dissemination	sales and subscriptions	sales management
		IT	website
POST-PUBLISHING	Dissemination	hosting	hosting provision
		archiving/preservation	deposit of content and metadata in archiving/preservation services
POST-PUBLISHING	Dissemination	editorial control	reviewing texts in terms of content/quality and fit in terms of scope
		copy editing and proofreading	reviewing texts to improve literary quality and checking compliance with editorial rules/house style and eliminate typographical mistakes
POST-PUBLISHING	Dissemination	graphic design	designing the graphics/layout of the editorial product
		cover design	
POST-PUBLISHING	Dissemination	supplemental materials preparation	video, audio files etc.
		typesetting/layout/formatting	arranging text and images on the page according to the graphic design/layout
POST-PUBLISHING	Dissemination	metadata creation	attribution and maintenance of bibliographic metadata according to FAIR and open principles
		translation	
POST-PUBLISHING	Dissemination	print production	
		persistent identifier (PIDs) attribution	attribution of identifiers, such as ISSN, ISBN, Open Researcher and Contributor Identifier (ORCID), Digital Object Identifiers (DOI)
POST-PUBLISHING	Dissemination	xml conversion	full text conversion to xml format for online publication
		epub production	text processing/conversion to generate files in ePub format
POST-PUBLISHING	Dissemination	pdf creation	text processing/conversion to generate files in PDF format
		enhanced editions	production of digital publications with augmented, enriched, multimedia content
POST-PUBLISHING	Dissemination	promotion	promotion via traditional tools (newsletters, conferences, etc.)
		social media	promotion and marketing via social media
POST-PUBLISHING	Dissemination	blog	blog creation and management
		review copies	sending digital review copies for pieces in journals, newspapers, magazines and other media outlets
POST-PUBLISHING	Dissemination	quality assessment	undertaking activities to demonstrate the academic quality and value of the project
		database/platform application	application and follow-up to add publications to selective databases and platforms, including library discovery services and search engine optimization
POST-PUBLISHING	Dissemination	indexing/abstracting services	application and follow-up to add publications to bibliographic and subject indexes and abstracting services
		metrics	provision of statistics and metrics services to measure publications impact

Image 4: List of the possible typologies of services to include in the Pathfinder.

Subsequently, a short list of providers was selected. In agreement with the OPERAS coordination team, they have been invited to submit their services for inclusion in the Pathfinder (in addition to Lexis itself, whose activities also include those of publishing services providers).

The fact that each was a member of OPERAS, it was considered a sufficient assurance of their credibility, without the need for further selection criteria:

- Georg-August-University Göttingen – UGOE
- OAPEN
- Open Books Publishers
- Open Edition
- Public Knowledge Project – PKP
- Ubiquity Press
- UCL Press
- UiT The Arctic University of Norway

In addition to the above mentioned services list, the invitation email included:

- A form to be filled in for each service offered (01_SERVICE.docx)

01_SERVICE.docx

SERVICE: *the name given to the service/service bundle from your institution/company*

DESCRIPTION: *the description of the service, what it actually delivers (max 2400 characters)*

SERVICE TYPE: *refer to column C of the table 02_SERVICES-LIST.xlsx*

PUBLICATION PHASE: *refer to column A of the table 02_SERVICES-LIST.xlsx*

SERVICE FAMILY: *refer to column B of the table 02_SERVICES-LIST.xlsx*

URL: *the page to refer to for the service, if any (please specify the full URL, i.e. https://www....)*

TARGET: *select one or more of the following options according to the target group for the service*
 - Editor (see the users description in Guidelines)
 - Editorial manager (see the users description in Guidelines)

LANGUAGE OFFERING: *which languages are accepted for the publishing services*

LOCATION OFFERING: *select one of the following options to indicate in which geographical areas the service is provided*
 - Global
 - Europe-wide
 - Nation-wide: *specify which countries*

SERVICE DELIVERY MODEL: *the requirement to be met by the user to access the service (for a fee, after validation of the application, only to members of a single university, etc.) (max 2400 characters). If this service is non-separable from other services you are providing, please indicate which services this delivery model is linked to.*

FORMATS: *to what editorial format the service applies (e.g. journal, book, blog...)*

STANDARDS: *if this service complies with international standards please indicate it here (e.g. Web Content Accessibility Guideline WCAG for accessibility...), with the related full URL*

KEYWORDS: *please enter here some keywords (or tags if you prefer) relevant to your service description, highlighted by previous descriptive texts, or additional, to make the service more effectively discoverable by the Pathfinder search engine*

Image 5: The form to use for the description of a service

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- A standardised profile description form (03_SERVICE-PROVIDER.docx)

03_SERVICE-PROVIDER.docx

Name: *the name of the organisation providing the service(s)*

Description: *you should describe the organisation here, not the service (max 2400 characters)*

Location: *office(s) address(es)*

Logo: *high-definition logo (.jpg .tiff or .eps, min. 300 dpi), to be sent as a separate attachment*

Url: *please include the full URL, i.e. https://www....*

Financial and Administrative profile: *please describe how the organisation you are presenting is managed in financial and administration terms (e. g. no profit, profit, funded, public, private, scholar-led, non-scholar-led... max 2400 characters)*

Contact (name and email): *the contact address the Pathfinder user can refer to for further inquiries and/or to request your services*

Certifications: *if your organisation is provided with some sort of certification, please indicate it here (ISO 9001, SA...)*

Keywords: *please enter keywords (or tags if you prefer) relevant to your Service Provider profile, highlighted by previous descriptive texts, or additional, in order to make the your organisation more discoverable by the Pathfinder search engine*

Image 6: The form to use for the description of the service provider

- Guidelines to facilitate the correct interpretation and filling in of the forms (pathfinder_guidelines.pdf)

PATHFINDER GUIDELINES

Pathfinder aims at helping editors and editorial managers find publishing services they could use to perform their editorial tasks and responsibilities. This service, developed in the context of several OPERAS projects funded by the European Union, is dedicated to open access publications in social sciences and humanities, such as journals, books, editions and other research outputs. Pathfinder works as a marketplace where scholarly communication services are offered by OPERAS members to researchers acting as authors, editors and editorial managers to support their work and improve quality.

Service **users** are identified as follows:

- **Editors:** scholars (but not exclusively) in charge of specific editorial tasks (e.g. select, handle, and prepare materials for publication) for a journal, a book series or another type of editorial project.,
- **Editorial managers:** scholars (but not exclusively) leading editorial teams and boards and having final responsibility for production and publication of research outputs. Editorial managers can be journals editors-in-chief, book series lead editors and/or directors of scholar-led (but not exclusively) publishers, librarians involved in providing advice and services to scholars or in managing library publishing services.

Authors, scholars looking for a book or journal publisher to publish their research with are not the primary target of the Pathfinder service, they are therefore redirected towards [DOAB](#) and [DOAJ](#) where they can discover quality checked open access journals and book publishers that may fit their needs. Additional resources are recommended to them, such as the [OA book toolkit](#) and the [Think. Check. Submit](#) service.

To list **your services** within Pathfinder, we ask you to complete and return the attached forms. In order to ensure high quality of the data that will be stored in the service, we ask you to read the **guidelines we provide to you**.

Our team will review your application to ensure compliance with the project's aims and overall uniformity. The revised version of the text will be submitted to you for approval before uploading to the database.

1. You will find attached to this e-mail a file called **01_SERVICE.docx**: this is the form you will have to fill in for *each* editorial service offered.

Use one form for each service (you can also create a single file with one page/form for each service). In case of services that are not provided individually but make up a bundle, fill in only one form for each bundle.

Where we ask for a description, the response must not exceed 2,400 characters. Each entry contains an explanation of what information needs to be entered.

We ask you to pay particular attention to the differences between:

* **DESCRIPTION:** the description of the service itself, what is actually delivered

* **SERVICE DELIVERY MODEL:** the requirement to be met by the users to access the service (for a fee, by application, etc.)

2. You will find the list of publishing services currently included in Pathfinder in the attached file **02_SERVICES-LIST.xlsx**.

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The main column to refer to is C (SERVICE NAME), the columns PHASE and FAMILY are functional to the design of the platform, while in the DISAMBIGUATION column we included an explanation/description to help you understand what we mean by that specific service name (thanks to Graham Stone, JISC, for the discussion about this taxonomy, which will be further refined to become common heritage of OPERAS). We are of course available for any clarification. If we have not taken into account the existence of any service your institution/company provides, please let us know and we will consider including them in the search engine (notice: the services to be included in Pathfinder must all be strictly related to academic publishing).

3. Finally, **03_SERVICE-PROVIDER.docx**, is a presentation sheet for the organisation providing the services. For each entry there is an explanation to make it clear what information needs to be entered.

Image 7: Guidelines to help service providers to fill-in the forms

Those who responded positively to the invitation, within the deadline compatible with the drafting of this deliverable were: OAPEN, UiT The Arctic University of Norway (Septentrio) and Ubiquity Press. So, with the addition of Lexis, as of 31 Aug 2023 there are 4 providers who have their services included in this first release of the Pathfinder database.

The dialogue with the providers (both those who have actually already provided their data and those who have declared their intention to do so at a later stage), carried out by Lexis, enables the data entry system to be further refined and validated, incorporating the suggestions made where appropriate. Lexis will continue to take care of this task until the end of OPERAS-PLUS even though T5.3 has a formal deadline of 31 Aug 2023. Moreover, within WP8, especially Task 8.1 (Communication and Outreach), which runs until the end of the project (M36), Lexis (in cooperation with the task leader) will continue activities related to Pathfinder to invite an increasing number of providers to join.

Finally, until the end of OPERAS-PLUS, Lexis will be responsible for the collection, curation, updating and maintenance of the data entered, in direct dialogue with the participating providers. Any decision and policy in this regard will always be shared with the OPERAS Service and Technology Board (STB), of which Lexis is a member.

It is expected that over time the OPERAS STB itself will be responsible for making decisions on what to include in the catalogue, and how updates should be managed to align with the latest changelogs of services and tools, as well as formalising the process of identifying potential catalogue candidates, taking into account community recommendations and best practices, and possibly producing questionnaires and surveys.

4.2.2. Components, technical architecture and dependencies

High-level service architecture	Type	Service Components	Description	Suppliers	TRL
	Enabling	Cloud hosting	Where the whole architecture of the Pathfinder is installed. The service is provided by Net7 through the Hetzner cloud provider.	Net7 / Hetzner	9
	Enabling	Data Layer	Where Pathfinder data are stored. For the polyglot persistence principle, two servers are used for managing the platforms' data: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RDBMS (MariaDB) as the main repository • A search server (Elasticsearch), to enable text search and guarantee lower response times 	Net7	7
	Enabling	Back-end	REST APIs developed in PHP with the Laravel framework	Net7	7

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	Enabling	Front-end	REST APIs developed in PHP with the Laravel framework	Net7	7
	Enabling	Back-office	A web application, accessible only to authenticated users, for both managing data entries and administrative tasks, incl. managing vocabularies and users. It is based on the Backpack library, a Laravel plug-in (PHP).	Net7	7
	Enabling	OPERAS ID	Centralised identity management and single sign-on	OPERAS	9
	Enhancing	OPERAS Messaging	Allow users to exchange suggestions, ask questions and community building. A dedicated workspace (team) has been created for the Pathfinder on this Mattermost instance.	OPERAS	9

Service Dependencies	Service	Description	Organisation	Component Criticality	TRL
	OPERAS ID	For user registration & authentication	OPERAS	High	9
	Messaging	For the community aspects of the Pathfinder	OPERAS	Medium	9
	GoTriple widget	For the widget in the home page showing some updates from this platform	OPERAS	Low	9
	VERA widget	For the widget in the home page showing	OPERAS	Low	9

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		some updates from this platform			
Monitoring	<p>The Pathfinder has been deployed at Net7’s server farm, hosted at the Hetzner provider.</p> <p>Monitoring is done via Net7’s Nagios monitoring platform. The checks allow to verify the:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Availability of the front-end • Correct functioning of the search service • Availability of the back-office • State of the server, in terms of free disk space. <p>Similar monitoring requirements for any service provider, if decision to change.</p>				

Table 4: Service Architecture

4.3. Service Order Workflow

Step	Role	Description
1	Customer (Service Provider)	Service provider submits a completed service description form and sends it to Lexis for inclusion in the platform.
2	User	Searches, finds and selects a service. Clicks “visit service provider page” and is redirected
3	Customer (Service Provider)	Responsible for managing the user service request based on its own procedures

Table 5: Service Order Workflow

4.4. Service Acceptance Criteria

Category	Acceptance Criteria	Critical	Achieved	Instructions
Functional and technical acceptance	Correct deployment	Yes	Yes	Pathfinder in operation, with correct behaviour.
	Complete implementation	Yes	Yes	Functional verifications through a test plan.
Service level and reporting	Monitoring platform activated.	Yes	Yes	Monitoring performed through Net7's Nagios.
	Ticketing service for reporting issues.	Yes	Yes	OPERAS Jira integrated for ticket management and incident tracking.
Customer and supplier related	Acceptance of the test plan report by OPERAS	Yes	Yes	Functional verifications through a test plan.

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Capacity, availability, and performance-related	Capacity to sustain a sound number of concurrent users	Yes	Yes	Stress testing added in the test plan.
Security and data protection-related	Terms of Use and Privacy Policy	Yes	Yes	Managed through lubenda
Support related	Integration with OPERAS JIRA ticketing system	Yes	Yes	Activation and proper functioning of the "Report an issue" button.
Configuration, change and release related	<p>Ticketing systems for both end users and stakeholders and the development team.</p> <p>Service components added to OPERAS Configuration Management Database (CMDB)</p>	No	Yes	<p>Development changes managed through Net7's GitLab development management platform.</p> <p>Requests can be proposed via OPERAS JIRA</p>
Usability related	Functional testing via desktop (different	Yes	Yes	Functional verifications

	browsers) and via mobile (at iPhone and Android)			through a test plan
Organisational	OPERAS must have full ownership of the service.	Yes	Yes	Sharing with OPERAS stakeholder admin credentials to the Pathfinder back-office and development management platform.
	OLAs in place with service component providers	No	Yes	Prepare and sign OLA
Other	N/A	-	-	

Table 6: Service Acceptance Criteria

4.5. Service Options

#	Name	Description
1	Pathfinder	No other options

Table 7: Service Options

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4.6. Service Requests

#	Name	Description
1	“Report an issue” widget	It allows users to file requests or to report incidents in OPERAS Jira based ticketing system.
2	Lost password	Reset password via OPERAS ID

Table 8: Service Requests

4.7. Financial Structure

4.7.1. Costs

Item	Cost (PM or €)
Pathfinder development and data collection/curation and data entry for the whole duration of OPERAS-PLUS	€63.000 (14PMs): Net7 personnel budget €40.000 (10PMs): Lexis personnel budget TOT: €103.000
Hosting for 4 years	€4.000 (€1000*4)
Operations and maintenance (post-OPERAS-PLUS)	1 FTE: €51,000/yr
Development of new functionality and features (post-OPERAS-PLUS)	4 PMs: €17,000/yr

Table 9: Service Costs

4.7.2. Pricing Scheme

Item	Price
N/A	No pricing scheme is foreseen in the short-to-medium term. Potential fees could be introduced, i.e. freemium or fixed fees, for autonomous data curation by service providers.

Table 10: Pricing Scheme

4.7.3. Revenue Streams and/or Cost Recovery Measures

Revenue Source	Expected revenue (if applicable) Amount or a % of costs	Additional Info
OPERAS	1-100%	Alternatively if any central funding is available via OPERAS, then this can be used to fully or partly fund the service.
Service Providers	1-100%	Pricing scheme not yet defined, so the % and number of service providers to breakeven TBD

Table 11: Revenue Streams and/or Cost Recovery Measures

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5. Service Transition Plan

5.1. Transition Plan

	Activities and timing	Responsibilities (RACI)	Progress report
Specification, negotiation and agreement	Done in the course of OPERAS-PLUS	T5.3/WP5	DONE
Development and procurement	Done in the course of OPERAS-PLUS	T5.3/WP5	DONE
Initial testing	July 2023	Net7 / Lexis / OPERAS	DONE
Operation with early life support	From June 2023	Net7 / Lexis / OPERAS	DONE
Regular operation	From end of August 2023	Net7 / Lexis / OPERAS	PLANNED
Communication	From end of August 2023	OPERAS Communication team	PLANNED

Table 12: Transition Plan

5.2. Supporting Projects

Project name	Related task(s)	Activity Description	Period of activity	Effort (PMs)	Status
OPERAS-PLUS	T5.3	Net7: design of the service, UX/UI design software development, operation, hosting Lexis: design of the service, content collection and curation, data entry	Sep 2022 - Aug 2023	25	COMPLETE

Table 13: Supporting Projects

5.3. Final Service Phase Check-list

Service phase	Responsible	Description	Condition met	Notes / Evidence	Verification
Alpha Min. maturity = TRL5	Luca De Santis	T5.3 Task leader	First version of the Pathfinder installed in production	Platform public accessible, yet under access control	Correct functioning of the front-end and the back-office components
Beta Min. maturity = TRL7	Luca De Santis	T5.3 Task leader	Updated version of the Pathfinder installed in production	Platform public accessible, yet under access control	User registration and authentication correctly implemented. User personalised services (kits)

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					working correctly. All alpha functionalities are still working correctly.
Production Min. maturity = TRL8	Luca De Santis	T5.3 Task leader	Pathfinder development complete	Pathfinder in operation Test plan report validated by OPERAS	Pathfinder online with all of its designed functionalities

Table 14: Final Service Phase Check-list

6. Current Service Overview

In this section, the technical implementation of the Pathfinder is described by covering all phases of the work, from the initial User Research process and UI design, up until the definition of its software architecture and the development of all its components.

6.1. User research

To better shape the implementation of the new Pathfinder, a user centered design approach has been followed. The purpose was in fact to create a service that would completely fulfil the needs of its intended target audience. To reach this goal, a user research activity has been conducted: it was based on two interactive workshops, with each session focusing on specific scopes.

The first workshop was centered around co-mapping the publication journey for directors, editors, service providers and authors. This collaborative exercise allowed the participants to visually outline the key touchpoints, decisions, actors involved, obstacles and useful metrics that come into play during the pre-publication, publication and post-publication phases. The outcome was a collective user journey map (see image below) that served as a comprehensive guide for understanding the entire publication workflow.

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Image 9: User journey map of the publication workflow

In the second workshop, the focus was on testing the service types proposed by Lexis to classify the possible offerings of service providers, grouped in the three main phases of the editorial workflow: pre-publication, publication and post-publication. Participants were actively engaged in exploring and evaluating the services to gain insights into their positioning in the various phases and their actual usefulness for editors and editorial managers. The intention was to enhance the service-finding process of the Pathfinder and create a seamless experience for the users.

The workshops involved a selected group of participants: the first one was dedicated to the Italian publishing community and included two directors and an editor, while in the second two directors, an editor and a service provider were involved. This diverse mix of stakeholders allowed for a well-rounded understanding of the various perspectives and needs within the publication process. The first session took place on 21 December 2022, while the second was scheduled on 20 January 2023. Each workshop spanned a duration of two hours, ensuring that adequate time was available for meaningful discussions and insights to emerge.

These virtual workshops were conducted on-line via Zoom: in addition FigJam, a digital whiteboard platform, was used to facilitate the mapping and visualisation of ideas, making the process engaging and interactive for all participants.

The workshops helped to define the characteristics that the Pathfinder should guarantee: by optimising connections between users, services and service providers, the platform can streamline the process of service discovery. This optimisation aims to reduce the time-consuming search for services, ultimately benefiting all stakeholders involved.

Finally, the input gathered via this process, allowed the creation of the "wireframes", which, as shown in the images that follow, consist of a first simplified version of the Pathfinder's user interface that, after having received an approval by project partners, guided the actual design phase of the platform, described in the section that follows.

Image 10: Pathfinder's wireframes

6.2. Design of the Pathfinder

Pathfinder is an editorial research platform designed to transform the way editors and editorial managers connect in discovering publishing services. With a responsive design and seamless user experience, Pathfinder, integrated within the OPERAS ecosystem, offers a comprehensive range of features.

Through its intuitive homepage, search capabilities, detailed service/provider pages and personalised "Kit" space, it simplifies the process of finding and engaging with service providers.

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Image 11: Pathfinder's UI

Pathfinder's design focuses on delivering a visually appealing and user-friendly interface. The platform's key components and functionalities include:

- **Responsive Design:** Pathfinder's design ensures optimal user experience across various devices, adapting seamlessly to different screen sizes and resolutions.
- **Homepage:** The homepage serves as a compelling entry point, providing a concise summary of the platform's purpose and benefits. Users are immediately introduced to the value proposition of Pathfinder, emphasising its ability to connect editors and managers with service providers efficiently.
- **Service/Provider Search:** The platform integrates a search engine that enables

users to discover a range of service providers based on specific criteria such as service family, description, location, and languages offered. This search functionality ensures users can quickly find relevant options tailored to their unique requirements.

- **Detailed Service/Provider Pages:** Pathfinder provides dedicated pages for each service or provider, offering comprehensive details like descriptions, qualifications, location, format, standards, and contact info. Users can make informed decisions that align with their needs.
- **Pathfinder's customizable "Kit" space:** lets users create and organise collections of favourite services, streamlining access and saving time. It also enables easy sharing with team members for seamless collaboration.
- **Wizard:** that allows you to customise your search: Pathfinder incorporates a wizard that empowers users to personalise their search experience.
- **User account:** designed to collect minimal user data.

Image 12: Pathfinder's UI

Pathfinder's design meticulously follows the guidelines of the OPERAS-PLUS brand. The platform incorporates graphical elements, typography and interface components that align with the brand's colours, typography, shapes and Tone of Voice. This cohesive integration within the OPERAS ecosystem ensures a consistent and delightful user journey.

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Pathfinder's innovative design and user-centred approach, based on the research described in the previous section (8.1), redefine the editorial research landscape. The platform simplifies discovering and engaging with service providers with its responsive design, intuitive interface and features. Pathfinder delivers a visually appealing and trustworthy experience by adhering to the OPERAS-PLUS brand guidelines. Pathfinder empowers editors and managers to make informed decisions, foster productive partnerships and drive excellence in the scholarly publishing domain.

6.3. Software architecture

The general overview of the service is depicted in the diagram that follows:

Image 13: Pathfinder's software architecture

It consists of a typical multilayered web architecture with:

- **Data Layer:** where the principle of “polyglot persistence” is applied, with a relational database (the open source MariaDB system) as the primary data

source and efficient text search server (Elasticsearch) added to boost searches and, in general, performance on data access.

- **Back-end:** The application's business logic is implemented in PHP using the Laravel framework. The functionalities are then exposed through REST APIs.
- **Front-end:** It consists of two components: the Back-Office administration interface, also implemented in PHP using the Backpack module of the Laravel framework; the interactive dashboard developed in TypeScript using the Angular framework.

The platform has been integrated with already existing OPERAS services, namely:

- **OPERAS ID** for users registration and authentication.
- **Mattermost**, where a dedicated Pathfinder workspace to allow users discussions has been created.

There is also a lightweight integration with the GoTriple and VERA platforms. On the Pathfinder home page, we present some updates from these two platforms as a strategy to improve mutual visibility amongst OPERAS services.

6.4. Data model

The Pathfinder data model is formed by:

- The main data entities that are considered are: *Services*, the “core” of the project, and *Service providers*, who provide services. We assume that there is only one Service Provider per Service.
- *Controlled Vocabularies*, used to classify Services and Service Providers.

The relationship between Services, Service Providers and Vocabularies is shown in the picture below.

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Image 14: Pathfinder's data model

The data entities are defined as follows:

Services

Field	Type	Notes
ID	ID	Main identification of the service
Name	String	--
Provider	Reference	ID of the Service provider
Description	Text	--

Service type	Controlled vocabulary	This attribute can be multivalued
Bundle	Boolean	Indicates that a service is composed of multiple single services (therefore with multiple Service Types) that cannot be acquired separately
Publication phase	Select from a list of values	Pre-publication Publication Post-publication
Service families	Controlled vocabulary	--
URL	String	--
Target	Select from a list of values	Editorial Manager Editor
Language offering	Controlled vocabulary	--
Location offering	Select from a list of values.	Global Europe-wide Nation-wide
Supported nations	Controlled vocabulary	Only if in the previous field "Nation-wide" has been selected
Service delivery model	Text	--
Formats	Controlled vocabulary	--
Standards	Controlled vocabulary	--
Keywords	Controlled vocabulary	--

Table 15: Services data model

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Service Providers

Field	Type	Notes
ID	ID	Main identification of the service
Name	String	--
Description	Text	--
Location	Long Text	Array of JSON objects. Every object identifies a town and includes, amongst others, its long/lat coordinates, the name, country and ID in the Geonames linked data repository. Example: <pre>{ "lng": "12.51133", "lat": "41.89193", "name": "Rome", "toponymName": "Rome", "adminName": "Lazio", "externalId": 3169070, "countryName": "Italy", "countryCode": "IT" }</pre>
Language offering	Controlled vocabulary	--
Logo	String	The path of the file.
URL	String	--
Business model	Text	--
Contact name	String	--
Contact email	String	--
Certifications	Controlled vocabulary	--
Keywords	Controlled vocabulary	--

Table 16: Service Providers data model

The vocabularies currently defined in the Pathfinder are:

- Service type: the main taxonomy to classify services.
- Service family: grouping of services.
- Publication phase (NOT EDITABLE): pre-publication, publication, post-publication (see List of Services above).
- Target (NOT EDITABLE): it indicates to whom the service is addressed. Possible values are: Editor, Editorial Manager.
- Location offering (NOT EDITABLE): global, Europe-wide, nation-wide.
- Formats: Indicates the context in which the service can be applied.
- Standards: to be associated with services, a folksonomy whose categories can be added dynamically during data entry.
- Certifications: to be associated with service providers, folksonomy.
- Service keywords: Folksonomy.
- Service Provider keywords: Folksonomy.

The main assumptions related to the data model are:

- Services should have at least one Service type but they can have more than one, acquired singularly or only all together. In the last case, we have a “Bundle” option (see next point).
- Bundle: this is a boolean attribute associated with a Service. When True we assume that:
 - The service is a Bundle
 - The associated services cannot be provided separately
- Every Service type has a default Service family and a Publication phase.
- Location offering (Service): It consists of two elements: the type of location offering (global, Europe-wide, nation-wide) and, in case “nation-wide” is selected, the list of nations where the service can be provided. We assume to include in this case only European countries (at least initially).
- Location (Service provider): The same solution has been implemented in COESO’s VERA: the editor can select the town from a suggested list, implemented by using Geonames APIs. For each city, multiple attributes are then stored in the entity, including:
 - The label
 - The Country code
 - The long/lat

Albeit all these details are hidden to the editor, who simply sees the name of the town (see image below).

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Location

Image 15: Automatic suggestion of towns for the Location field

APIs are implemented to allow data to be searched for and presented in the Pathfinder's front-end (developed in Angular). These APIs use an Elasticsearch server where all data are indexed. The Elasticsearch index defined for this purpose contains two "documents", one for Services and one Service Providers.

The schema of these two Elasticsearch documents reflects the structure of the Service and the Service Provider entities, with some considerations:

- A Service provider must automatically inherit some attributes from its Services. So specific fields, populated automatically, must be added in the document structure. These are:
 - Target (Role)
 - Publication phase
- Some attributes have been configured to use them as faceting filters. In particular:
 - Service:
 - Provider
 - Service type
 - Bundle
 - Publication phase
 - Service family
 - Target
 - Location (only the "type", that is global, Europe-Wide, nation-wide)
 - Bundle/Number of service types
 - Formats (hidden in the Front-end for the moment)

- Standards
 - Service keywords
- Service provider:
 - Location - Country
 - Certifications
 - Service provider keywords
 - Role (inherited by its services)
 - Publication phase (inherited by its services).

An indexing service has been developed to asynchronously (by using Laravel queues) indexes Elasticsearch each time data changes in the back-office. Each time a Service or a Service provider is inserted, updated or deleted, Elasticsearch must be updated.

6.5. Search and data access APIs

The search and data access APIs that have been implemented are as follows:

- Services: search api, with the possibility to specify a full text query and with the filters indicated above. The full text must be “boosted” on the service name

Sort: relevance, name alphabetical, creation date, modification date

- Service/{id}: to return the detailed information of a single service
- ServiceProviders: search api, with the possibility to specify a full text query and with the filters indicated above. The full text must be “boosted” on the service provider name

Sort: relevance, name alphabetical, creation date, modification date

- ServiceProvider/{id}: to return the detailed information of a single service provider

6.6. Predefined searches and wizard

Pathfinder has a page for Editors and Managers that presents to users a list of common searches and a search wizard. The difference is that a common search is just a link that executes a search directly; with the wizard, the user is guided in specifying the parameters of the search. In both cases, the query is executed on the Services index.

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They can be configured from the platform back-office: we refer both as “configurable searches”.

For every one of them, in the back-end an administrator can specify:

- A name/label
- A description
- Type: common search vs wizard
- Target (optional): Editors or Editorial Managers (or none)
- Zero or more steps. If there are no steps it consists of a common search, otherwise it is a wizard. For every step you have to specify
 - A label
 - The number of the step, to be used for ordering (alternative solutions for that can be considered)
 - An Elasticsearch variable (for Services)
 - Types of possibilities for users' selection
 - All the possible values that the variable can assume (like a facet aggregation)
 - A list of possible values for this variable that the user must select (label, value). The user can select more than one value
 - A free string that the user can write
- An Elasticsearch search URL (on Services).

The latter, in case of steps, will appended the conditions specified at every step, e.g.

`<search URL>&variable=value`

In the front-end it is possible to:

- Retrieve all configurable searches matching a certain criteria (e.g. target, type)
- For a common search: clicking on a its label directly activates the Elasticsearch search URL
- For a wizard: it guides the user to choose the values for every step before running the Elasticsearch query, with the added conditions specified at the steps.

6.7. Registration and services for registered users

Personalised services for the Pathfinder are simple. A user can:

1. Register via OPERAS ID⁶
2. See her/his account settings (basically just showing the information fetched from the OPERAS ID)
3. Manage the “kits” in lists.

A kit is a list of services chosen by the user. A user can have as many kits as they want. Kits can be shared, therefore they can be viewed by any other user, without the need to be authenticated to the Pathfinder.

As far as the registration is concerned, the implementation followed what has already been implemented for other OPERAS services, namely for GoTriple and VERA. In particular, the signup must bring to a page where the user should first accept the terms and conditions plus the privacy policy. Then the link redirects to the “Create an account” page of the OPERAS ID⁷.

The authentication, on the other hand, brings the user directly to the main page of the OPERAS ID.

The menu for registered users is composed of the following 3 elements:

- Account settings
- My “Kits”
- Logout

As done in GoTriple, the account settings entry only shows the minimum information coming from the OPERAS ID (name, surname, email and photo). To change them, the user must go to the OPERAS ID.

As said, the Kits consist of personalised lists of Services (not Service Providers). Users can add a service to a kit from the:

- Service search result page
- Landing page of a service.

An icon identifies the possibility of adding the service to a kit. If a user is anonymous,

⁶ <https://id.operas-eu.org/>

⁷ <https://id.operas-eu.org/register>

clicking on this icon will bring to the login/registration form: after this, the user will be able to add the Service to a (new) kit.

If the user is authenticated, an interface appears to allow the user to add the service to:

- An existing kit
- A new one.

When creating a new kit, the user must specify a name and an optional description.

By clicking on the “My kits” voice of the registered user menu, the user sees all the lists that have been created. Each list can be:

- Deleted
- Viewed/edited (removing existing Services, renaming or changing its description)
- Shared.

The last option produces a user-friendly url that the user can send to other people.

6.8. Front-end implementation

6.8.1. Overview

The Pathfinder front-end has been developed with Angular v14 framework using TypeScript language and currently provides a dedicated page for the home, the search, the authors and a detail page for services and service providers. Each page is represented as an Angular module in a specific directory, and it is loaded as a child module whenever the router path matches one of the specified configurations in the app routing module.

Any available interaction with the filters, pagination or query in the search page is handled as an independent link that updates the routing parameters. As a result, the page component keeps listening to router changes so that anytime it happens, a function builds a new request using its parameters that will later update the internal state.

Most parameters are parsed beforehand to prevent the front-end application from making a request that will mostly encounter a failure in the API call.

Some UI elements in the templates have been created from Angular Bootstrap available components with style customisation; this is the case of the accordion used

for the filters in the search page, modals, search tabs, etc.

Image 16: Pathfinder front-end UI components

The internationalisations (i18n), currently available only in English, has been implemented using the ngx-translate library that keeps key-value pairs in a JSON file for each configured language and allows the translations to be accessed either via its own Http Loader module or simply using a pipe.

The codebase has a simple structure, other than its own description file and routing configuration file. Each module has two directories: the logic and the views.

6.8.2. Component views and logic

The views directory holds the Angular component, which is made of the HTML template and the TypeScript (TS) file class that handles its behaviour.

The logic contains the TS files that hold and manage global or local state, expose a sort of internal APIs for obtaining slices of it, act as intermediary for API data requests and handle the necessary operations based on the requested action.

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Image 17: Structure of the Pathfinder front-end app

This is made possible using the NgRx libraries by splitting the previously described operations into five logic components:

- Actions: they define a signature of the possible actions a component is able to make
- Effects: they implement the side effects operations to be executed as a result of an action
- Reducers: they contain the logic that manipulates the internal state by returning an updated deep copy, made using the lodash library, as a result of an action.
- Selectors: they implement functions exposed to retrieve slices of state
- States: they define the initial state of the store

Some effects are responsible for making service calls to retrieve data. That means they invoke a function stored in the service directory that makes a GET or POST call to an API endpoint using the basic HttpClient from Angular.

Image 18: Logic components of the Pathfinder front-end app

7. Conclusions

This deliverable provided an overview of the implementation of the Pathfinder within Task 5.3 of OPERAS-PLUS. The official release of the platform represents a significant milestone in the project, offering support to editors and editorial managers throughout their open access publication process and suggesting authors with valuable resources to publish the results of their research.

In addition to detailing the software development process, this document has examined the role of Pathfinder as a service within the OPERAS ecosystem.

It is important to point out that the work on the Pathfinder is not finished with its go-live. In fact, the platform's significance will continue to grow over time.

This growth will be driven by ongoing editorial activities that continue throughout the remainder of the OPERAS-PLUS project and are aimed at expanding Pathfinder's catalogue with information about new services and service providers.

Furthermore, as an OPERAS service, the visibility and relevance of the platform are expected to grow, thanks to the dissemination activities conducted both within the OPERAS-PLUS project and across other OPERAS-related initiatives.

These endeavours will contribute to expanding the platform's user base, increasing its impact and outreach within the SSH community.

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